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"ANCHORED BY FAITH, DRIVEN BY DETERMINATION"

"Poverty is not a hindrance to success."

This has been the guiding principle that has inspired and pushed me to bravely face the many challenges I encountered along life's unpredictable journey.

As the daughter of a coconut farm worker and a humble housewife, I consider my roots to be my lucky charm—then, now, and always. Being the eldest of three siblings, I grew up with a strong sense of responsibility. From a young age, I understood the weight of that role. My elementary and high school years were far from easy. Though filled with joyful memories, they were also marked by sacrifices. I walked several kilometers to and from school each day just to save money for the next day's "baon." Even as a child, I knew the value of saving my allowance—not spending on snacks but instead setting aside every peso to buy materials for school projects and other requirements.

With our limited resources, the dream of going to college felt impossible—even though I graduated from high school with flying colors. But I refused to let that stop me. I worked harder, determined not to let negative thoughts drown my dreams. Holding onto my belief in the power of perseverance, I kept chasing my vision and looked for every possible way to make it a reality.

That's when the idea of applying for a scholarship came to me—my stepping stone to continue the journey I had started. To my surprise and immense joy, I was accepted into the **UCPB-CIIF Foundation Scholarship Program**. Getting there wasn't easy—the path was steep and full of challenges—but every struggle was worth it. Through faith, determination, and God's grace, I passed and became a proud scholar under the **COCO Foundation**.

The scholarship opened doors for me as I pursued my college education. I proudly carried the title of Cocomer scholar then, and I always will. My university years were a mix of experiences—some fulfilling, others challenging. I once had a professor who underestimated me, but I proved myself capable. I skipped meals just to stretch my allowance and make it through the week. University life was a battlefield, and while I suffered losses along the way, I never stopped fighting. And in the end, I won.

With faith and determination, I earned my **Bachelor of Science in Agriculture, major in Agricultural Business**, and in the same year, passed the **Licensure Examination for Agriculturists**. My hardships were

never stumbling blocks—they were stepping stones, each one preparing me for success through resilience and perseverance.

But the journey didn't end there. With two younger sisters still in college, I was motivated to work harder to help my parents support them. I worked as a guest college instructor at my alma mater and simultaneously pursued my master's degree. It was a tough balancing act, but I stayed focused and optimistic.

Then life threw me a heartbreaking challenge—the unexpected passing of my beloved mother. She was my inspiration, my biggest fan, my steadfast supporter, and my partner in every step I took. Her absence left an overwhelming void and unimaginable pain. But as the eldest, I had to be strong—for my sisters, who still needed guidance. I took on the role of a mother while silently grieving and longing for mine.

Despite this painful loss, God's compassion never wavered. He continued to bless us. Today, both of my sisters are professionals, excelling in their respective fields. That is a triumph greater than any title. I didn't just achieve my dream—I helped fulfill my family's dreams as well.

I proudly graduated my Masters' Degree. I am eternally grateful to **scholarship benefactor**. Their support extended beyond financial aid—they uplifted me spiritually and morally. Words may never fully capture my gratitude, but I offer them from the depths of my heart. Thank you for being the instrument of God's grace in my life.

